

Application of LiDAR and neuromorphic vision in ambient assisted living environments

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Abstract: The non-invasive monitoring of patients is especially important in the field of ambient assisted living environments to increase acceptance of such systems and the use of cameras. The goal of this work was to test two specific systems in their viability to monitor a patient and detect vital-parameters like the respiration rate. A Lidar system was successfully used to detect people in a room, using a fine-tuned neural network while neuromorphic cameras were used to detect the respiration rate in patients while still considering privacy.

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I. Introduction

The non-invasive monitoring of patients and their vital parameters is gaining significance in the medical field, partly due to the rise of novel vision technologies and the use of artificial intelligence in data processing. Two of these technologies are LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) and neuromorphic vision sensors, which significantly differ from conventional cameras in the way that they acquire their data and allow the consideration of privacy as faces are not directly identifiable. The goal of this work is to evaluate the use of these technologies in ambient assisted living applications [1] and the general measurement of vital-parameters.

I.1. LiDAR and neuromorphic vision

The first technology, used in this work is LiDAR. A remote sensing method using laser pulses for 3D mappings of environments [2], which is widely applied in fields like autonomous vehicles and environmental monitoring [3]. The use of LiDAR in the medical field is largely unexplored, just like the use of neuromorphic vision sensors. Neuromorphic vision sensors imitate the way the human eye and brain process visual information as they do not acquire frames in fixed time intervals, but monitor the change of illumination for every single pixel asynchronously, transmitting data only for pixels with occurring events. Neuromorphic vision systems are used in many applications that require fast machine vision like robotics, autonomous driving [4] or the space industry. The use of neuromorphic cameras in the medical field offers promising new approaches for contactless monitoring of patients and their vital parameters.

II. Material and methods

The LiDAR used in this work is the OSDDome by Ouster, optimized for indoor spatial analysis and navigation with a 180° field of view. This sensor ensures full spatial coverage with exact tracking and detection.

The neuromorphic camera is a DVXplorer by Inivation vision system with a resolution of 640 x 480 event pixels, a latency of < 1 ms and a maximum throughput of 165 MEPS (mega events per second).

Both systems were deployed in a room, solely designated to the development of ambient assisted living applications. The LiDAR was mounted upside-down in the room and was used for object detection purposes. To detect humans in the LiDAR data, the object detection model Yolov5 has been fine-tuned with images from the LiDAR system to enhance the accuracy. After the fine-tuning, it was possible to use Ouster's Python SDK to facilitate seamless communication between the sensor and the host machine. The data then had to be converted to images, compatible with the YOLOv5 model which was integrated into the Python-based pipeline.

The neuromorphic camera was placed on a desk where the test subject would sit, with the camera focused to the chest area of the subject, making it possible to detect movement of the chest caused by respiration. For ground truth measurements of the respiration rate, a Hamilton C3 respirator, equipped with a flow sensor, was used. The test subjects sat in front of the camera before and after doing physical exercise which consisted of a light jog on a treadmill for at least 5 minutes. The data were acquired and processed in a Python script which made use of a software library, provided by Inivation for acquisition of the data and processing libraries like SciPy and Matplotlib which provided the necessary filters and visualization methods. To extract the respiration rate, a Savitzky-Golay filter with a frame length of 55 and a polynomial order of 2 was applied. The filtered event data for the respiration rate is displayed in fig. 1. The respiration rate was then calculated by detecting the peaks in the signal, extracting their timestamps and using the median value of the distances between each pair of peaks to be robust against the natural variations of the quasi-periodic [5] respiration rate and

against possible false positives when detecting the peaks in the data.

Figure 1: Variation of event activity with visible respiration

III. Results and discussion

The calculated results and the ground truth measurements of the event data is shown in table 1. The mean absolute error (MAE) for the resting respiration rate is 1 bpm for the resting rate and 0.525 bpm for the active respiration rate which can also be attributed to different methods and time windows used to calculate the respiration rate, compared to the Hamilton-C3 device. In other works, evaluating the concept of contactless respiration-rate monitoring, MAEs of less than 1 have been achieved. [6]

Table 1: Respiration measurements in bpm

Subject	Ground truth RR (Resting/Active)	Detected RR (Resting/Active)	Error
1	17/24	18/22	1/-1
2	18/25	17.6/24.4	-0.4/-0.6
3	19/24	17.9/24	-1.1/0
4	14/-	16.8/-	2.2/-
5	20/24	19.7/23.5	-0.3/-0.5

The analysis of the fine-tuned YOLOv5 model shows that the model training had a positive impact on the performance. In Fig. 2 the untrained model detects a single person with a confidence level of 53 %, failing to detect another human in the scene. This shows potential limitations of the model, when handling data beyond its training. The trained model showed obvious improvement, detecting two persons in the scene, as seen in figure 3. This underscores the benefit of targeted training on LiDAR data.

Figure 2: Untrained YOLOv5 model detection

Figure 3: YOLO OD performance with trained model

IV. Conclusions

This research shows the capabilities of LiDAR systems and neuromorphic vision cameras in ambient assisted living environments. The detection of people in a room and their activity as well as the monitoring of their heart rate can play an important part in providing remote around-the-clock care. The inherent properties of neuromorphic cameras and LiDAR sensors also provide a solution with enhanced privacy.

Improvement can still be made in the algorithms for detecting people and calculating the respiration rate, by collecting data from more test subjects and adding more classes to the object detection model. More research will also be done to test the feasibility of using neuromorphic vision systems for respiration rate in different conditions like movement of the patient and in different positions.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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